

CHARACTERISATION OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES USING HIGH RESOLUTION DISTRIBUTED FIBRE OPTIC SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

The reliable prediction of the behaviour and failure mechanisms of composite structure is challenging. This is in large part due to the inherent heterogeneity of these materials introduced by the weaving or stitching of the reinforcing fibre bundles into fabrics. Modelling methods typically assume homogeneous properties for individual lamina or even the laminate as a whole to simplify the process. In reality, the material properties vary locally and the effects of these local variations on the structural response are difficult to predict and characterise.

Recent developments which combine continuous fibre gratings (CFGs) with optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR) interrogation techniques have enhanced the ability to provide low noise, distributed fibre strain sensing with submillimetre resolution. This paper describes an experimental investigation into the use of these sensors to detect and characterise material inhomogeneity and damage in a range of fibre reinforced composite specimens.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre optic strain sensors are a popular candidate for integration within composites to enable material state awareness due to their intrinsic compatibility with the host material. There are a number of sensing options available which can be broadly classified into two distinct categories: discrete and distributed. Discrete strain sensing systems rely on sensors introduced into the fibre at discrete locations [1]. These systems can only measure strain at the points where a sensor is present. The most common discrete fibre optic sensor for the measurement of strain is the fibre Bragg grating (FBG) [2].

Distributed sensing uses the entire fibre as the sensor. These sensing systems typically rely on backscattered light from the optical fibre [3,4]. The backscattered profile is unique to each fibre, and is a function of position. It can be modelled as a long, weakly reflecting FBG with a random period. Changes in the local period of the backscatter caused by an external stimulus such as strain will cause a shift in the locally reflected spectrum. These local spectral shifts can then be characterised using optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR) and calibrated to form a distributed strain and/or temperature measurement. As backscattering is a naturally occurring phenomenon, distributed sensing can be achieved using standard single mode telecommunications fibre which is readily available and extremely cost-effective.

Several commercially available systems have emerged for the measurement of strain using optical fibres, providing either multiplexed point sensing via the use of fibre Bragg gratings (FBGs) or distributed sensing from the backscattered light, which naturally occurs in the fibre. FBG based sensing typically offers a better signal to noise ratio (SNR) and the capacity for more rapid interrogation of the signal, whereas distributed systems provide strain measurements with a much higher spatial resolution at a significantly lower cost per sensing point. More recently, the use of continuous fibre gratings (CFGs) combined with OFDR interrogation techniques have emerged as a compromise between these two systems, providing good sub-millimetre resolution with reflected light levels strong enough to improve the SNR when compared to conventional backscattering techniques. This paper reports on an experimental investigation into the use of these sensors to detect and

characterise both material inhomogeneity and damage in a series of fibre reinforced composite materials and structures.

2 CHARACTERISATION OF MATERIAL INHOMOGENEITIES

Eight fibre reinforced composite coupons comprising four different lay-up designs were manufactured according to Table 1. All coupons were manufactured using vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM). A long pot life epoxy manufactured by ATL Composites (Kinetix R118/H103) was used as the matrix resin. The coupons were produced to incorporate a range of different weave geometries and final thicknesses in both glass and carbon.

Contact profilometry was used to characterise the surface profile of the release (bag) side of each coupon in order to account for any local variations in coupon thickness in the model. This data was used to produce a geometrically accurate FEA model of each coupon with a fine tetrahedral mesh (COMSOL Multiphysics). The principal strains in the loading direction were predicted for each coupon using smeared orthotropic material properties. The elastic constants used for the model were experimentally measured on materials produced using the same VARTM process.

A two metre CFG sensing fibre was bonded to the tool side of each coupon in seven parallel sensing lines aligned to the loading axis using a thin layer of cyanoacrylate as shown in Figure 1. The bonded sections of the sensing fibre provided approximately 2000 strain measurement points across a measurement region of 180 mm x 30-40 mm (depending on the coupon) from which a two dimensional strain map could be generated. Each coupon was loaded in tension in a mechanical test machine to achieve an average strain level in the coupon of approximately 2000 $\mu\epsilon$.

<i>Properties</i>	<i>Coupons 1,2</i>	<i>Coupons 3,4</i>	<i>Coupons 5,6</i>	<i>Coupons 7,8</i>
Material	Non crimp E-glass biaxial 600 g/m ²	E-glass: Basket weave 150 g/m ² , Carbon: Non crimp uniaxial 450 g/m ² Carbon Non crimp: Double Bias ± 45 400 g/m ²	Carbon: Non crimp Double Bias 400 g/m ²	E-glass : Satin weave 600 g/m ²
Lay-up	[+-45] _{g7}	0 _g , [0, ± 45 , 90, ± 45 , 0] _c , 0 _g	[0] _{c8}	[0, 90] _{g11}
Dimensions	400 mm x 50 mm x 4 mm	400 mm x 50 mm x 2.7 mm	400 mm x 50 mm x 3.6 mm	400 mm x 50 mm x 8.5 mm

Table 1: Lay-up geometries of different composite coupon designs

Figure 1: CFG sensing fibre bonded to test coupon under tensile loading in mechanical test machine.

Figure 2 shows the strain distribution along the loading axis for each coupon design under tension. In each sub-figure, the left and right images show the measured strain distribution and the modelled strain distribution, respectively. Also included for each coupon are images of the weave geometries. The coupon in figure 2(a) is made of non-crimp glass fabric which has a coarse weave geometry. The experimentally measured strain distribution reflects the ply orientation and weave geometry. The model predictions for the same coupons show no discernible pattern in the distribution. The coupon in figure 2(b) comprises multiple layers of different materials, orientations and weave geometries. Here, there is a significant feature running transversely across the coupon at approximately 200 mm observed in both the experimental measurements and model predictions. This feature is consistent with a local variation in coupon thickness which occurred at this position. In addition to this, the experimental measurement also shows strain variations which reflect the weave geometry of the high stiffness uniaxial carbon layers. In figure 2(c), the coupon was fabricated from double bias carbon fabric and again the experimental strain measurement showed a significant variation in strain with a pattern that was consistent with the weave geometry. The model predictions for this coupon showed a very small variation in strain with a pattern which was consistent with the surface features of the coupon. The coupon shown in figure 2(d) was a thick e-glass coupon with 22 plies of satin weave material. As expected, due to the number of plies and the fine weave geometry, the experimentally measured strain variation is much less significant than for the other coupons with a distribution which is not consistent with the ply weave geometry. The experimentally measured percentage strain variation for this coupon is 7% compared with 31%, 21% and 15% for coupons 1, 3 and 5

respectively.

Figure 2: Images depicting the measured (left of sub-figure) and predicted (right of sub-figure) strain distributions for (a) coupon 1, (b) coupon 3, (c) coupon 5 and (d) coupon 7. Images of the weave geometry used for each coupon are shown to the right of each sub-figure.

3 RESPONSE TO DAMAGE

Two composite test articles were examined using CFG sensing fibres to characterise the response to damage under load. The first, was a carbon fibre plate $[45,0,0,-45,90]_{3s}$ with dimensions 100 mm x 250 mm x 4 mm which was subjected to three successive impacts (5 joules, 5 joules and 21 joules

respectively) to induce barely visible impact damage. The coupon was then loaded in a mechanical test machine to characterise the distributed strain response of the coupon under tensile load. A 2 metre CFG sensing fibre was bonded in seven parallel lines on the rear side of the plate to provide approximately 1200 sensing points from which the strain distribution in the loading axis could be generated under a static strain survey from 5 to 40 kN in 5 kN increments. Figure 3 shows measured strain distribution from the impacted plate together with a phased array ultrasonic image from the upper surface. Both images clearly show the damage with similar sizing and orientation. In addition, the in situ-strain measurement shows the effect of damage on the structural response of the plate providing valuable information about structural health.

Figure 3(a): Phased array ultrasound of impact damaged composite plate, (b) Experimental Strain distribution measured using CFG sensing fibre under 40 kN load.

The second test article was a composite hydrofoil comprising a 300 mm active and 110 mm root span region. The root cord was 120 mm while the tip cord was 60 mm. A schematic representation of the hydrofoil geometry is shown in Figure 4. A trapezoidal planform of the hydrofoil was selected in order to investigate the loading conditions typically found in hydrodynamic lifting bodies such as marine propellers, rudders, and control surfaces without added geometric complexities [5]. The profile of the hydrofoil was based on a NACA 0009 aerofoil [6] modified to produce a thicker trailing edge (from a half thickness of 0.095% to 0.66% cord) to minimise the risk of fracture during demoulding and under experimentation. A 2 metre CFG sensing fibre was stitched into the outermost structural ply in 4 parallel sensing lines during the lay-up process.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram showing foil dimensions

The hydrofoil was loaded in a cantilevered configuration (Figure 5) using a screw driven mechanical loading machine (Instron 5500R). The hydrofoil was anchored at its root in a profiled aluminium capture block. Incremental loads were applied via a profiled aluminium formboard located near the tip such that the hydrofoil deflected upwards with the sensors located on the underside of the foil. The edges of both the capture block and formboard had generous radii to reduce their effect on local stress concentrations.

Figure 5: Cantilever configuration with load application point at tip position (no load applied).

The loading schedule applied a series of slow linear ramps, increasing incrementally in maximum amplitude until structural failure occurred in the hydrofoil. Fourteen trials were conducted in total with the maximum load increasing from 1.75 kN to 4.75 kN. The load was applied near the tip of the hydrofoil as indicated in Figure 5 so as to maximise the active sensing region within the hydrofoil. Figure 6(a) shows the internal ply lay-up from one half of the hydrofoil, 6(b) the measured strain distribution at a load of 2.25 kN prior to structural failure, 6(c) and (d) the measured strain distribution at a load of 0.60 kN pre and post structural failure respectively.

As expected, the overall strain in the foil was predominantly in tension with a distribution which was broadly consistent with the ply drop offs. There were some compressive strains induced near the tip clamp due to torsional loads that develop from the hydrodynamic profile of the foil. There were five localised regions of strain concentration running chord wise at approximately 100 mm, 150 mm, 170 mm, 200 mm and 250 mm from the top of the foil. The first region (100 mm) is located at the boundary between the foil capture block and the unconstrained area of the foil. The stress concentrations at 150 and 250 mm were aligned with span wise ply drop-offs as shown in Figure 6(a). The strain concentrations which occur at approximately 170 and 200 mm do not align with a span wise drop-off however there is a taper in the ply layers which result in an effective drop-off for the sensing fibres in this region. These results suggest that the CFG sensor can provide an indicator of the internal geometry of the hydrofoil together with their influence on the structural response.

The foil failed abruptly by an internal delamination at a load of 4.75 kN. After failure the load was ramped a final time to assess the strain distribution post failure. Figures 6(c) and 6(d) contrast the strain distribution pre and post structural failure of the hydrofoil under the same load of 0.6 kN. The strain levels in the failed region of the foil indicate an approximately four fold increase which is consistent with the load-displacement curves from the same test pre and post failure. The region of elevated strain in the failed region of the foil indicates the failure zone extends to approximately 200 mm from the root in a region where there are a large number of chord wise drop offs.

Figure 6: Plots depicting (a) the hydrofoil internal ply lay-up, (b) the pre-failure strain distribution under 2.25 kN load, (c) the pre-failure strain distribution under 0.60 kN load, and (d) the post-failure strain distribution under 0.60 kN load.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reports on an experimental investigation into the application of a new class of fibre optic strain sensor (continuous fibre gratings) combined with optical frequency domain reflectometry to provide high resolution spatially resolved strain measurements in composite materials. The strain data provides sufficient fidelity to characterise not only the influence of damage, but also the effects of material inhomogeneity on the structural response under loading.

The experimental data indicates that local variations in the strain response of undamaged composite structure can be associated with the weave architecture of the reinforcing plies, particularly for thin coupons with a coarse ply weave. Regions of damage could also be located and sized from the strain response under loading with additional insights provided into the effect of the local damage on the global structural response. The increased fidelity of the experimental measurements can be useful as an aid for model validation, the optimisation of lay-up design and to better understand the failure modes of composites.

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